

INSURANCE RISKS AND THEIR IMPACT ON THE FINANCIAL STABILITY OF INSURANCE COMPANIES

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Annotation: The article describes the role of the insurance method in the effective management of investment risks in the national economy. The analysis of the impact of insurance risks on the financial stability of insurance companies is considered.

Key words: Insurance fund, citizens and organizations, insurance contracts, risk assessment, risk management, investment risks, investment potential of the insurance company, assessment and analysis of investment projects.

In society, citizens and their team have appropriate social relations with each other in the course of their activities. In order to standardize these relations, it is necessary to regulate them, that is, it is necessary to determine the scope of actions of citizens and organizations. The above applies to full insurance. Insurance as a socio-economic legality requires strengthening from the legal side. Relations that arise in the process of establishing and using the insurance fund are regulated by law.

Legal relations arising in the field of insurance are part of civil-legal relations. Such relations regulate the legal status of the participants in civil transactions, property rights and other material rights, contractual obligations, as well as property and personal non-property relations.

• Civil-legal relations in the field of insurance are manifested in the following directions:

- civil-legal relations formed between citizens and insurance organizations;
- mutual relations between insurance organizations;
- civil-legal relations between citizens and special state bodies;
- civil-legal relations arising between insurance organizations and a specially authorized state body.

It is the main condition for the emergence of risk-insurance relations. If there is no risk, there can be no insurance. The size and quantity of the risk is determined using the methods of probability theory and mathematical statistics. Analysis of insurance risks requires dividing them into 2 large groups. That is,

the risk is insured and uninsured. Risks reflected in insurance contracts are called insurance risks. The expression of the risk assessment in money is the insurance rate. Risk is not a constant indicator, it is constantly changing. These changes are closely related to changes in the economy and other areas. The insurance organization must constantly monitor the development and status of the risk, that is, it must conduct appropriate statistical calculations, process and analyze the collected data.

To assess the risk, it can be divided into the following types:

- 1) Insurable risks.
- 2) Uninsurable risks.

Insurable risks are the largest group of risks. Insurance risks can be distinguished from uninsured risks based on the following criteria.

The risk must be random;

- Uncertainty of the time and place of occurrence of insurance events;
- Risks according to the source of risk are risks related to natural forces and risks related to the impact of humanity on nature due to the exploitation of material wealth.

In the classification of risks, major catastrophic risks have a special place. As a result of the occurrence of such risks, many objects can suffer a large amount of damage. Earthquakes, tsunamis, and strong winds can be examples of major catastrophic risks. In addition to the above-mentioned risks, there may be environmental, political and special risks.

Risk control is the monitoring of the condition of the insured object and its preservation by the representative of the insurance company. It is also checked whether it meets the requirements of storage hazard. Necessary recommendations and tips for good storage of a number of objects are given.

Risk financing is the covering of all costs related to risk identification, assessment and control.

-The fact that insurance relations have a distributive character. Like the concept of finance, insurance also participates in the redistribution of gross domestic product and national income.

- Distribution of losses in insurance by regions and at a certain time. This is the main feature of insurance, which requires a large area and a large number of insurable objects to distribute the insurance fund among insured farms. will be done. The distribution of losses at a certain time is due to the fact that insurance events have the character of random occurrence. Emergency incidents may not

occur for many years. This situation requires the establishment of adequate insurance reserves when insurance events do not occur.

- Refund of insurance premiums involved in insurance funds. Insurance premiums are determined based on the insurance tariff. The insurance tariff consists of two parts: the net rate (which is used to cover losses in the event of insurance events) and premiums to the net rate (which cover expenses related to the organization of the insurance company's work). The net rate is generally returned to the insured in the event of an insured event.

In accordance with the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the insurance conditions for the types of compulsory insurance are determined by legal documents. The amount of insurance tariffs for voluntary insurance is determined in accordance with the agreement of the parties.

Distribution of funds of the insurance fund only among the entities that participated in the establishment of this fund.

The following parties participate in insurance relations:

Insurers are legal entities that specialize in providing insurance services and have an appropriate license. An important link of business activity. According to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Insurance Activities", a legal entity that undertakes to pay insurance compensation (insurance money) in accordance with an insurance contract is considered an insurer. .

Insurers can have different forms of ownership (state insurance organizations, joint-stock insurance organizations, and mutual insurance companies). Organizations conducting insurance activities must have an appropriate license from state authorities.

The insured is a legal entity or individual who has established a specific insurance relationship with the insurer and pays the corresponding insurance premiums.

Insurance intermediaries are legal entities acting as mediators between the insurer and the insured. By its status, the intermediary protects the interests of the insured. For the services provided, the intermediary receives the appropriate brokerage fee from the insurance company, not from the insured.

The improvement of market relations is a process that goes hand in hand with the settlement of the economic infrastructure. Insurance activity as an integral part of the economic infrastructure, on the one hand, provides social security, and on the other hand, it also undertakes the protection of the interests of economic entities on the basis of warning against various insurance risks through the mechanism of contractual obligations and tariffs.

At this point, the existence of a system of special redistribution relations according to the forms of ownership, aimed at creating the possibility of ensuring continuity in production (performance of work, service), serves the development of economic entities. In this process, their interests such as ownership of property, its use and income are revealed.

Currently, the formation and development of risk transfer at the level of demand in the insurance activity in our country, as well as its study on a scientific basis, are gaining significant socio-economic importance. In particular, the expanding freedom of economic subjects, their adoption of new types of production (performance of work, service), increases the need for research and improvement of the scientific and theoretical basis of risk transfer in insurance activity.

In order to more fully reveal the socio-economic nature of insurance, it is appropriate to study approaches to this issue in scientific literature. It is mentioned in them that it is the "insurance-service industry"³, based on this, it can be noted that the "theory of the service economy" is gaining ground in the international economic terminology in the following years.

In terms of its essence, the concept of "service" is fundamental in insurance activity. The "service" offered by the insurer does not initially reflect materiality, that is, it only "sells a promise" to its client. From this point of view, it is also classified as "invisible activity"¹ in international trade. The insured is only given a "policy"² as a document confirming the conclusion of the contract. The insurance contract stipulates that the insured will be provided with a monetary payment (in some cases in the form of property) equivalent to the loss he is likely to suffer in accordance with the insured event. The execution of the CONTRACT will be carried out within a certain period specified in it.

It is observed that there are always risks in the process of the formation and development of market relations step by step, the high level of economic independence and freedom of economic subjects in our country. Insurance deals with the special service of re-distribution of risks that may harm their interests and is constantly recurring.

"Insurance means the payment of insurance compensation (insurance money) to these persons in accordance with the insurance contract in the event of a certain event (insurance event) at the expense of funds formed from insurance premiums paid by legal entities or individuals. protection of their interests is understood

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